

Sexual Violence and the Making of the Anti-Heroine in Contemporary Nigerian Women's Fiction

Fatima Jennifer Omachonu

Ifeyinwa Okolo

Abba A. Abba

Department of English and Literary Studies

Federal University Lokoja, Nigeria

Abstract

This article examines how sexual violence and its aftermath shape the development of the anti-heroines in two contemporary Nigerian novels: Yejide Kilanko's *Daughters Who Walk This Path* and Oyinkan Braithwaite's *My Sister, the Serial Killer*. It argues that sexual violence in these novels is not presented merely as individual trauma but as a systemic feature of a typical patriarchal society, one that generates complex, morally ambiguous female characters. The article explores how Kilanko and Braithwaite subvert traditional tropes of female victimhood drawing on a mélange of feminist theoretical perspectives of Andrea Dworkin's and Catharine MacKinnon's radical feminist frameworks, bell hooks' intersectional insights, and Judith Butler's conception of subjection. Within the framework of these respective theories, female protagonists resist, survive, and reconstitute themselves as anti-heroines: characters marked by resistance, ethical compromise, and agency within repressive systems. Through this analysis, the article positions contemporary Nigerian women's fiction as a site of feminist intervention that interrogates both local and global gender politics.

Keywords: sexual violence, anti-heroine, trauma, patriarchy, gendered resistance

Introduction

Contemporary Nigerian women's literature increasingly engages with themes of violence, identity, and gender resistance. In recent decades, a growing number of female authors have interrogated the complex realities of women's lives, particularly the ways in which patriarchal structures shape female subjectivities. Among these, Yejide Kilanko's *Daughters Who Walk This Path* and Oyinkan Braithwaite's *My Sister, the Serial Killer* offer distinct but related explorations of the lasting psychological, social, and moral impact of sexual violence. Through their respective protagonists, Morayo and Korede, both texts challenge the conventions of heroism, foregrounding the emergence of the anti-heroine as a figure marked by trauma, resistance, and moral ambiguity. This paper investigates how sexual violence functions not simply as a trauma generating occurrence but as a transformative force which catalyses the development of the anti-heroine in both novels. It argues that these texts deploy sexual violence to critique both overt and covert systems of patriarchal domination, from either the familial context or to the larger societal level. More importantly, the paper critiques the traditional binary between victimhood and heroism by presenting protagonists who inhabit an uneasy space between ethical resistance and survivalist complicity.

Central to this analysis, is the work of radical feminist theorists Andrea Dworkin and Catharine MacKinnon, whose foundational insights frame sexual violence as a political and structural phenomenon. Dworkin

argues that heterosexual relationships, as culturally and socially constructed, reproduce male dominance and female subordination. MacKinnon further articulates how law and culture function to normalise sexual violence, rendering women's trauma invisible within systems of legal and social authority. Their theories provide a critical framework through which the analyses of the protagonists in Kilanko's and Braithwaite's novels are shaped by the intersections of power, trauma, and resistance. Additionally, this study draws on Judith Butler's theory of subjection, bell hooks' insights on Black women's resistance, and Gayatri Spivak's caution about the erasure of the subaltern voice. Together, these feminist frameworks allow for an in-depth analysis of the novels not only as literary texts but as feminist interventions into Nigeria's social and political fabric realities. The protagonists in both novels are not passive recipients of violence; rather, they emerge as complex figures who grapple with their circumstances through ethically fraught choices. In so doing, they disrupt dominant narratives of idealised womanhood, offering a portrait of the anti-heroine.

By analysing these texts through a composite feminist literary lens, this article contributes to the growing body of scholarship on African women's writing, trauma narratives, and gendered resistance. It argues that Kilanko and Braithwaite do not merely represent trauma but actively reconfigure the literary space to accommodate female protagonists who resist victimhood without necessarily embodying idealised heroism. The anti-heroines that the respective narratives craft confront their pain, make difficult moral decisions, and challenge both patriarchal expectations and feminist idealisms. In so doing, these novels complicate our understanding of agency, survival, and resistance in contexts marked by gendered violence. The representation of sexual violence in literature, particularly within African feminist discourse, necessitates a multidimensional theoretical framework that considers both the socio-political context of the narrative and the psychological implications of trauma. In examining *Daughters Who Walk This Path* and *My Sister, the Serial Killer*, it becomes imperative that both texts operate within a cultural space where gendered violence is simultaneously systemic and deeply personal.

Radical feminist theory offers one of the earliest and most potent critiques of sexual violence as a structural problem rather than an isolated act. Andrea Dworkin posits that sexual violence is embedded in the very social construction of heterosexual relationships, where male dominance and female submission are often normalised and eroticised. Dworkin's work challenges the cultural narratives that depersonalise sexual assault by framing it as a routine consequence of patriarchy rather than an aberration. Her perspective is particularly pertinent to Kilanko's novel, where Morayo's abuse is facilitated and concealed within the familial home, an institution traditionally viewed as safe and nurturing. Catharine MacKinnon complements this argument by articulating the legal and ideological underpinnings that protect male character and the privilege that he enjoys in matters of sexual violence. MacKinnon demonstrates how legal systems often fail to recognise the coercive structures that silence women and enable perpetrators of violence against women. She redefines rape not simply as an act of force, but as an expression of unequal power relations, one often naturalised by social and cultural institutions. These insights are crucial to understanding how silence, complicity, and familial loyalty operate in Kilanko's text to shield male perpetrators of sexual violence like Bros. T from scrutiny. In Braithwaite's novel, this same theoretical parameter helps analyse

how the cultural devaluation of women's testimonies and the fetishisation of female beauty play into a system that indirectly justifies or ignores incidents of male violence. Judith Butler expands the discussion by considering the psychological processes through which subjects internalise oppression. Her concept of subjection, as the paradoxical process by which individuals become socially recognisable subjects through submission to power, helps to explain the complex positionality of Kilanko's Morayo and Braithwaite's Korede. Both characters are products of cultures that demand obedience and silence from the female character, yet such victims subvert these norms by refusing to be passive. Butler's framework allows us to see these protagonists not simply as victims or rebels, but as figures which emerge from pain as subjects capable of resistance, even when such resistance takes ethically troubling forms.

Bell Hooks interrogates the ways in which Black women's experiences of violence have been marginalised within both feminist and anti-racist discourses. Her insistence on centring the voices of Black women is mirrored in the narrative strategies employed by Kilanko and Braithwaite, both of whom prioritise the inner lives and ethical dilemmas of their protagonists. hooks' framework enables a close reading of Korede's ambivalence and Morayo's trauma, as both characters reflect the intersection of gender, race, class, and familial loyalty. Gayatri Chakravorty Spivak's warning about the risks of appropriating marginalised voices offers a critical reminder for the need to avoid simplistic readings of these novels. Although both novels are written by Nigerian women authors, they must still be read with a critical awareness of how trauma and resistance are culturally mediated. Spivak's call to attend to the silences within narrative, what is unsaid, what cannot be spoken, deepens our reading of the psychological interiority of these protagonists. Morayo's delayed disclosure of her abuse and Korede's coded journal entries exemplify how trauma resists linear articulation and must instead be read through gesture, implication, and silence.

These theoretical contributions converge in one central premise: that sexual violence is not merely a background condition but a structuring force within the lives of women. In *Daughters Who Walk This Path* and *My Sister, the Serial Killer*, the protagonists navigate societies and societal structures where violence against women is both common and, disturbingly, normalised. Yet they also resist this reality, not through overt heroism but through morally complicated decisions that enable their survival. This dual movement between subjection and resistance defines the anti-heroine, a figure who emerges not despite trauma but through it. By framing the protagonists through this intersectional feminist praxis, the article seeks to uncover the ethical and psychological complexities embedded in their narratives. The anti-heroine in these texts is not an idealised figure of feminist liberation, but a morally ambiguous subject who resists victimhood without transcending the social and psychological damage of violence. The feminist theories of Dworkin, MacKinnon, Butler, hooks, and Spivak offer the conceptual vocabulary necessary to engage these texts critically, allowing us to see how literature becomes a site of both critique and catharsis in the ongoing struggle against patriarchal violence.

A Synoptic Overview of the Texts

Yejide Kilanko's *Daughters Who Walk This Path* is a bildungsroman set in Ibadan, Nigeria, tracing the psychological and emotional development of Morayo, a bright and curious young girl whose life is

irrevocably changed by the sexual abuse she suffers at the hands of a trusted male relative, Bros T. The novel intricately documents Morayo's journey from innocence through betrayal and trauma, eventually to tentative healing and resilience. Kilanko foregrounds the silence surrounding sexual abuse within Nigerian families and critiques the societal complicity that enables such violence to persist. Through the character of Morayo and the guidance of Aunt Morenike, a fellow survivor, the novel situates and points at sexual violence as a recurring form of gender oppression, one frequently silenced by familial loyalty, religious conservatism, and cultural norms which account in many ways for female submissiveness. Her refusal to be defined solely by trauma complicates notions of the virtuous heroine, positioning her instead as an emerging anti-heroine who reclaims power through memory, narrative, and resistance.

Oyinkan Braithwaite's *My Sister, the Serial Killer*, on the other hand, employs satire, noir aesthetics, and psychological suspense to explore the blurred boundaries between complicity and survival in a Lagosian context. The novel is narrated by Korede, a stoic nurse and the older sister of Ayoola, a beautiful and charismatic woman who has killed multiple boyfriends under the guise of self-defence. The novel opens with Ayoola summoning Korede to help her dispose of a body, a task that Korede undertakes with alarming efficiency, suggesting that this is not the first time. While Ayoola appears carefree and manipulative, Korede wrestles with moral conflict, loyalty, and her own suppressed desires, especially when Ayoola begins dating Tade, a doctor Korede secretly admires. Braithwaite's novel plays with genre expectations to critique societal expectations of femininity, beauty, and familial duty. Korede, like Morayo, is not a conventionally admirable figure; she is complicit, morally conflicted, and emotionally repressed. Her decisions reflect the psychological toll of living in a society where women's voices are dismissed and beauty is weaponised. By narrating the story from Korede's perspective, Braithwaite offers a critical meditation on sisterhood, trauma, and ethical ambiguity, framing Korede as a modern anti-heroine shaped by violence, both direct and systemic. Despite their tonal and structural differences, both novels centre on female protagonists who are forced into ethical dilemmas by their proximity to sexual violence. In *Daughters Who Walk This Path*, the violence is direct and shattering, leading Morayo into a long and painful process of self-recovery. In *My Sister, the Serial Killer*, the violence is mediated through Korede's role as a passive enabler and reluctant accomplice, resulting in a complex entanglement of guilt, resentment, and familial obligation. Both texts refuse to offer clear moral resolutions, instead presenting characters who act out of necessity rather than virtue. In doing so, they align with the literary tradition of the anti-heroine, flawed, reactive, and radically human.

Sexual Violence in *Daughters Who Walk This Path* and *My Sister, the Serial Killer*

Kilanko's *Daughters Who Walk This Path* presents a harrowing yet deeply reflective portrayal of sexual violence, exploring its psychological and societal impacts. The novel follows Morayo, a young Nigerian girl, whose coming of age is abruptly disrupted by sexual abuse, exposing how patriarchal silence, familial complicity, and systemic neglect shape the lives of many young girls in Nigeria. Kilanko deftly portrays the complexity of trauma within a cultural context where victimhood is muted by shame, and where institutions fail to protect the vulnerable. Morayo's trauma begins within what should be the safest space:

her extended family. Her cousin, Bros T, emerges not as a monstrous outsider but as a trusted figure, further complicating the dynamics of power and betrayal. His grooming process is subtle and insidious: “He started bringing me sweets, whispering in my ears, and giving me longer hugs” (Kilanko 45). This seemingly benign affection masks a calculated manipulation that culminates in repeated sexual assaults. Morayo, silenced by fear and confusion, internalises the violence: “I didn’t understand what was happening, but I knew it was wrong. I felt dirty” (Kilanko 49). Her experience reflects what Andrea Dworkin defines as the patriarchal script of domination, where male violence is naturalised, and female suffering is rendered invisible (Dworkin 24).

Catherine MacKinnon argues that sexuality, in patriarchal systems, is structured in such a way that male pleasure and control are prioritised over female autonomy (MacKinnon 174). In Morayo’s case, Bros T asserts authority not only over her body but over her silence. His warning, “Don’t tell anyone. No one will believe you”, functions as a mechanism of psychological imprisonment (Kilanko 51). The threat is not merely about disbelief but about social exile, a fear that is culturally reinforced in communities where female chastity is bound to family honour. Morayo’s silence is also sustained by her mother’s inability to read her daughter’s withdrawal. When Morayo’s academic performance falters and she becomes socially detached, her mother’s response is discipline, not inquiry: “You need to focus on your books. Stop playing the victim” (Kilanko 57). This moment underscores the generational gap in recognising trauma and the cultural tendency to stigmatise survivors instead of offering them support. Kilanko critiques a society where motherhood is often constrained by respectability politics, and where sexual abuse is shrouded in euphemism and moral panic. Aunty Morenike’s character provides a vital counter-narrative. Herself a survivor of childhood rape and ostracism, she becomes the first adult to validate Morayo’s pain. In a moment of shared vulnerability, she tells Morayo: “You are not alone. This happened to me too. But I survived, and so will you” (Kilanko 98). This feminist act of witnessing and naming the unspeakable disrupts the cycle of silence and shame. Kilanko’s refusal to make Bros T face formal justice is a deliberate political commentary. His exile from the family home is portrayed not as punishment, but as avoidance. The novel reveals the systemic failure of legal and institutional frameworks that are either indifferent to or complicit in the face of gendered violence. Bros T is not reported to the police, and no legal recourse is pursued.

Furthermore, *Daughters Who Walk This Path* critiques the cultural silencing of female sexuality. Before the abuse, Morayo receives no education about bodily autonomy or consent. When she starts menstruating, her mother warns her vaguely: “From now on, don’t let any boy touch you. That’s how it starts” (Kilanko 32). Such euphemistic warnings do not empower girls; rather, they frame sexuality as dangerous and shameful. Alison Healicon argues that the taboo around female sexuality in African societies creates a dangerous vacuum in which abuse flourishes unchecked. Kilanko reinforces this critique by showing how Morayo’s ignorance and her family’s moralistic silence leave her unprotected.

In a different narrative mode, Braithwaite’s *My Sister, the Serial Killer* approaches sexual violence through the intertwined lenses of irony, trauma, and subversion. Unlike the more overt portrayal of sexual abuse in

Kilanko's *Daughters Who Walk This Path*, Braithwaite's narrative encrypts trauma within the dry, detached voice of its narrator, Korede. The novel explores the cumulative psychological burden of living in a violently patriarchal society and examines how sexual violence, even when not always narrated explicitly, leaves enduring scars on women's bodies, psyches, and moral frameworks. Here, trauma and violence are encoded in silence, family complicity, particularly in a society that polices and commodifies female bodies. The novel's violence revolves around Ayoola, Korede's younger sister and a self-proclaimed victim who repeatedly kills her lovers. The surface plot of Ayoola's serial murders is underpinned by a trauma narrative. In one revealing moment, Ayoola confesses to Korede, "I didn't mean to kill him... he was hurting me" (Braithwaite 34). The ambiguity of this statement introduces a question that haunts the novel: is Ayoola a murderer or a woman who has turned violence into a defensive response against repeated male aggression? The family's backstory deepens this tension. The sisters' father is described as an abusive patriarch who brutalised both his wife and daughters. Korede recalls, "Father said he would kill her, and he almost did" (Braithwaite 95). These memories delivered in Korede's characteristic understatement suggest a household where violence was routine, where male domination was enacted physically and psychologically. Andrea Dworkin's assertion that patriarchal homes are the training grounds for violence against women becomes chillingly apt in this context. Ayoola's resort to violence can thus be read as a perverse inheritance, a learned behaviour born of trauma rather than pathology. This intergenerational trauma is mirrored in Korede's conflicted morality. As the elder sister and narrator, she serves both as Ayoola's protector and her reluctant accomplice. Her internal monologue is riddled with resentment, guilt, and emotional repression: "She kills them, but I clean up the mess. That's what I've always done" (Braithwaite 10). The burden of silencing, cleaning, and concealing becomes symbolic of the way women are socialised to manage and contain male violence, whether as victims or silent witnesses. Catherine MacKinnon's claim that "women are socialised into the experience of being sexually violated" (MacKinnon 174) is embodied in Korede's resignation to this dynamic. The novel also critiques how societal institutions fail women. After Ayoola kills Femi, one of her lovers, she uses her beauty to evade suspicion. Femi's diary, discovered by Korede, details Ayoola's manipulations and the psychological torment he suffered. Yet, when Korede tries to share her concerns with a senior nurse, the latter dismisses them: "Pretty girls can't be killers, not really" (Braithwaite 88). The belief that beauty and victimhood are synonymous is deconstructed through Ayoola's character. She is conventionally beautiful, soft-spoken, and outwardly harmless, traits that allow her to weaponise the very femininity which a patriarchal society values. This echoes MacKinnon's argument that patriarchal definitions of femininity render women vulnerable and then refuse to believe that women are capable of agency, let alone violence (MacKinnon 219).

Unlike Morayo in *Daughters Who Walk This Path*, Ayoola does not articulate her trauma directly. The novel never provides a full confession, which explains why the reader is left in a state of uncertainty. This narrative strategy mirrors the silences that often surround sexual violence in the society. As Judith Herman notes, "the ordinary response to atrocities is to banish them from consciousness" (Herman 1). Ayoola may not remember, or may actively repress her own abuse. Her compulsive need to dominate and control her relationships suggests a reactive logic of pre-emption: strike before being struck. Korede undergoes a

subtler psychological disintegration. Her obsessive cleaning, “I scrub until my skin burns”, is emblematic of trauma’s psychosomatic manifestations (Braithwaite 29). She is constantly caught between loyalty and horror, sisterhood and complicity. Braithwaite uses Korede’s clinical tone as a mask that conceals deep emotional turmoil. This stylistic choice is profoundly effective in communicating the effects of unresolved trauma and this is what Gayatri Spivak calls the “unspeakable” residue of violence. While Spivak argues that the subaltern cannot speak within dominant structures, Braithwaite shows how women like Korede and Ayoola navigate this inability by withholding, deflecting, or distorting speech altogether.

Ultimately, *My Sister, the Serial Killer* critiques a society in which violence against women is not an aberration but an ingrained norm, perpetuated by institutions, aesthetic ideals, and familial expectations. Through Korede and Ayoola, Braithwaite explores the psychological toll of such a society on women, especially when they are forced into silence or compelled to retaliate in unsanctioned ways. By embedding sexual violence in the subtext rather than exposition, the novel compels readers to examine the layers of trauma that lie beneath appearances. The strength of the narrative lies in its refusal to offer resolution instead, it challenges readers to ask how many women must clean up the messes of violence before they are granted the space to express their own rage.

The Making of the Anti-Heroine in *Daughters Who Walk This Path* and *My Sister, the Serial Killer*

In *Daughters Who Walk This Path*, Morayo’s development as an anti-heroine emerges from traumatic experiences, her rejection of societal expectations, and her refusal to embody the idealised feminine virtues of silence, shame, and submission. Rather than conform to the archetype of the virtuous victim or the passive heroine, Morayo evolves into a self-aware, resistant figure who claims her own narrative, even when it defies cultural norms. This transformation, shaped by sexual violence, loss, and healing, aligns with feminist theories of anti-heroism that view female defiance not as moral failure, but as political resistance (Stewart, Spivey, and Knowlton 93). Initially, Morayo appears to be the quintessential “good girl”: intelligent, beautiful, obedient, and eager to please her parents. However, after the betrayal by Bros T, her moral universe is irrevocably altered. Her silence is not born of weakness but of survival, and when she finally begins to speak, it is not to seek public vindication but personal coherence. In this way, she rejects the binary of victim and victor. As Ruth Barcan argues, the anti-heroine often occupies a moral grey space, one shaped by necessity rather than choice (Barcan 15). Morayo’s choices, such as breaking off emotionally harmful relationships or refusing to forgive on command, are framed not as heroic gestures but as necessary acts of self-preservation.

What marks Morayo as an anti-heroine is her refusal to allow suffering to define her entirely, and her ability to embrace complexity without demanding redemption. She does not seek to avenge her trauma nor to publicly punish her abuser, but she also does not forgive him. When her mother asks, “Have you let it go?”, Morayo responds, “No. But I’ve stopped letting it hold me prisoner” (Kilanko 158). This refusal to perform closure is emblematic of the feminist anti-heroine: a figure who disrupts the narrative expectations of forgiveness, moral purity, and linear healing. Judith Butler argues that subjectivity is formed through

subjection, through the internalisation of norms that simultaneously constrain and enable identity (Butler 3). Morayo is subjected to gendered norms that require silence, chastity, and honour, but her resistance to these norms becomes the basis for her agency. Her identity as a survivor is not one of passive endurance but of active reconstruction. Her therapy, journaling, and candid reflection are political acts, reclaiming voice from a system that tried to render her voiceless.

Furthermore, Morayo does not exist in isolation. Her journey is paralleled and informed by the anti-heroic arc of Auntie Morenike. Cast out by her family and community, Morenike refuses shame and builds a life of purpose through mentoring other girls. She embodies what Meda Chesney-Lind calls “the feminist outlaw”, a woman who resists social norms not through violence or dominance, but through refusal and solidarity (Chesney-Lind 27). Morenike becomes a mirror for Morayo, showing that the path of the anti-heroine is not solitary but collective, grounded in community and resilience. Kilanko’s portrayal of anti-heroism is thus distinctly African feminist. The anti-heroine in *Daughters Who Walk This Path* is not a rebel without cause, but a survivor without apology. Her defiance is subtle but seismic: she chooses to speak, to remember, to heal, and most importantly, to exist beyond the roles ascribed to her. In doing so, she challenges both the patriarchal structures that harmed her and the literary traditions that would sentimentalise her suffering.

In *My Sister, the Serial Killer*, Oyinkan Braithwaite presents an anti-heroine whose construction is even more provocative and subversive than Kilanko’s Morayo. The novel revolves around two sisters, Ayoola, the beautiful serial killer, and Korede, the responsible nurse who cleans up after her crimes. Together, they form a dual anti-heroic axis that challenges normative assumptions about femininity, morality, and victimhood in contemporary Nigerian society. Unlike Morayo, whose rebellion is psychological and redemptive healing, Korede’s anti-heroism lies in her complicity, while Ayoola embodies a radical, almost allegorical rejection of patriarchal violence. Ayoola, the titular serial killer, fits no traditional mould of either heroine or villain. She is unapologetic, opaque, and indifferent to guilt. In the narrative, murders of romantic partners are not depicted as arbitrary or sadistic acts but rather as morally ambiguous responses shaped by systemic pattern to male aggression, entitlement, and abuse. In this way, Ayoola becomes what Rebecca Stewart terms “the anti-heroine born of retaliation”, a figure who “reverses gendered power dynamics by weaponising the same systems that have oppressed her” (Stewart 47). While her actions are criminal, they symbolically represent an inverted justice, killing not just men, but the structures that permit male domination.

Korede, in contrast to Ayoola, is the novel’s narrative centre and moral conscience, yet she is not a traditional heroine either. Her loyalty to her sister renders her morally complicit. She lies to the police, disposes of evidence, and remains silent despite her increasing suspicion that Ayoola is a manipulative and unrepentant killer. Her internal monologue is laced with resentment, jealousy, and suppressed rage. “I can’t help but wonder if the men Ayoola killed saw the signs,” she says. “If they looked into her face and saw past the beauty. If they glimpsed the blackness behind her eyes” (Braithwaite 76). Yet, even as she critiques Ayoola, Korede does not act against her. Her refusal to do so is not passivity, it is fear, guilt, trauma, and

love entangled. The complexity of Korede's character aligns with George Goethals and Scott Allison's theory of the reluctant hero, one who is propelled into action not by courage but by necessity and inner turmoil (Goethals and Allison 93). She is a caretaker caught between moral righteousness and familial loyalty, between personal safety and cultural silence. Korede is not brave, but she is perceptive. She sees the truth and cannot unsee it. Yet her decision to continue protecting Ayoola at the end of the novel marks her final descent into anti-heroism. This descent is rooted in trauma. The sisters' shared childhood is shaped by a violently abusive father, whose legacy haunts the narrative. In flashbacks, we see Ayoola as the favoured child and Korede as the overlooked one, each coping in her own way. Braithwaite hints that Ayoola may have killed their father in self-defence, a murder unspoken but not unremembered. This buried trauma offers a feminist reading of Ayoola's behaviour: her actions, while morally indefensible, are born from a system that taught her that power could only be seized through violence. Elaine Showalter argues that when women's characters transgress moral boundaries, they disrupt cultural anxieties about female agency (Showalter 72). Ayoola's beauty, charm, and violence expose the shallowness of patriarchal expectations. Her success in escaping scrutiny underscores how society prioritises appearance and charm over substance. She is the ultimate anti-heroine, that is, morally suspect, narratively compelling, and politically disruptive. Korede, internalises her trauma, her guilt, and her complicity. Her role as nurse symbolises care and preservation, yet her actual life is dominated by secrets and decay. She saves lives at work while covering up deaths at home. Her anti-heroism lies not in action, but in inaction, that is, in her refusal to choose justice over kinship. This refusal challenges the moral absolutism often imposed on women in fiction. As Terry Eagleton suggests that the anti-heroine resists coherence and thrives in contradiction (Eagleton 165).

Braithwaite refuses to punish either of the sisters. Ayoola remains free; Korede remains silent. The novel ends not with a resolution but with a repetition of the cycle of silence. This unresolved ending reinforces the novel's feminist politics: justice is elusive, morality is murky, and survival is often secured at the expense of virtue. The anti-heroine in *My Sister, the Serial Killer* is not a corrective figure; she is a revelation of what happens when society denies women the power to express rage, trauma, and desire without fear of reprisal.

Conclusion

This article has examined how Kilanko's *Daughters Who Walk This Path* and Braithwaite's *My Sister, the Serial Killer* complicate traditional notions of femininity and heroism through their portrayal of sexual violence and the making of the anti-heroine. Both Kilanko and Braithwaite foreground female experiences of trauma, resistance, and moral ambiguity, challenging dominant narratives of victimhood and virtue. The anti-heroines in these novels disrupt binary moral frameworks by embracing complexity, refusing silence, and asserting agency on their own terms. Their stories underscore the systemic nature of sexual violence and the difficulties of attaining justice within patriarchal societies. Ultimately, these contemporary Nigerian women's fictional narratives offer powerful feminist critiques and reimaginings of survival, healing, and female subjectivity.

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